

Computer-Aided Detection of Lung Cancer from CT-scan Images with Visual Insights using Deep Convolutional Neural Network

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Highlights:

- This study finds models with the best-mixed loss and accuracy achieved by the Xception Weighting model.
- ResNet50V2 Weighting and Xception Weighting showed almost perfect performance rather than without the weighting method with the highest test accuracy (99.11) and AUC score (99.99).
- The Class Activation Maps from the two transfer learning models and the result was accurate in detecting abnormal lung features generated from the tumor presence.
- Proposed model could be used as a supplement in clinical decision-making.

Abstract. Lung cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide, reach up to 13% of all cancer diagnose with 273 million cancer cases in Indonesia alone. Lung cancer has a high mortality rate caused by difficulty in diagnosing cancer in the early stage. In the practice, if doctors suspected abnormality by CT examination, a cytological diagnosis of lung cells collected by biopsy is first performed. However, this method has a major challenge with malignant lung cell classification. This becomes a problem because early detection is the first step to reduce the mortality rate of lung cancer. In this study, we aimed to automatize the classification of lung cancer from CT scan images using Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN), fine-tuned ResNet 50V2, and fine-tuned Xception. CT scan images were acquired from the IQ-OTHNCCD lung cancer dataset. The original CT scan images first resize to 224x224 pixels. We obtained 416 normal, 120 benign, and 561 malignant CT scan images. The classification precision and

accuracy with highest performance achieved by Xception Weighting model with 99.11% accuracy, 99.11% F1 score, and 99.99% AUC score.

Keywords: *image classification; lung cancer; weighting; CNN*

1 Introduction

Cancer is one of the most serious health problems in the world. Lung cancer is the leading cause of death among men in the United States, Europe, and Asian countries [1]. In 2020 there are 273 million cancer cases in Indonesia alone [2]. In Indonesia, lung cancer is the third most common cancer case, with breast and cervix uteri cancer being the most common cases. Lung cancer is a type of cancer with the highest mortality rate caused by uncontrolled cells growth. The cells develop after much genetic damage to DNA that affects the cell's normal functions such as proliferation, apoptosis, and DNA repair [3]. These cancer cells can grow and spread beyond the lung in a process called metastasis. Although technology in medicine is already offering various treatment options like surgery, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy, the five-year survival rate for patients is still quite low. However, the survival rate may go up to 54% in case lung cancer is identified in the early stage [4].

Lung cancer is quite difficult to diagnose in the early stage, this leads to a higher risk factor and mortality rate. It's difficult to diagnose because many of the symptoms of lung cancer such as coughing up blood and shortness of breath are not specific [3]. In many cases, the malignant tumor has already spread beyond the original site before it gets medical attention [5].

Early-stage cancer detection and treatment are necessary to improve the survival rate among lung cancer patients. Chest radiograph and computed tomography (CT) become a standard modality for detecting and assessing lung cancer. CT screening able to reduces the mortality of lung cancer by 20% and prove as an

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effective diagnostic tool for early detection [6]. Therefore, to enhance the efficiency of lung cancer early detection, automatic analysis of CT-scan images and minimized false negatives are needed to shorten diagnosis time.

One method that can be used is computer-aided detection. Our focus in this study is automatically detecting lung cancer cells from CT scan images using deep automatic models. This method offers some advantages such as non-invasive method, accurate, and can obtain preliminary characterization that can be used to obtain faster and more precise diagnoses.

Several studies have shown computer-aided diagnosis based on computed tomography that gives satisfying results with high accuracy on bone cancer, breast cancer, even for cases as complicated as brain cancer. Computer-based classification using a deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) can outperform conventional image classification techniques for the classification of medical images [7]. This study uses the DCNN method to classify CT scan images into benign and malignant tumors.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Dataset

The Dataset that had been used to trained and tested the classifier is taken from the IQ-OTHNCCD lung cancer dataset [8]. There are 1190 images contained in the dataset which consisted of 416 normal images, 120 benign lung tumor images, and 561 malignant tumor images. All of the images in the dataset are in JPEG (Joint Photographic Expert Group) grayscale format and having a resolution of 512x512. Figure 1 shows one example from each class in the IQ-OTHNCCD lung cancer dataset. The dataset is then split 80:10:10 to create training, validation,

and test sets. The total number of images contained in the training, validation, and test sets were 876, 109, and 112 images.

Figure 1 Data samples from the dataset that shows each class

2.2 Weighting

The distribution of data in the IQ-OTHNCCD lung cancer dataset was imbalanced. To deal with the imbalanced data, the data are weighted to compensate for the difference in quantity. The weighting is performed by decreasing the majority class weights and increasing the minority class weight [9]. The weighting is done using compute class weight method from scikit-learn framework.

2.3 Data Preprocessing and Augmentation

The data have to be preprocessed before fed into the deep neural network. Data preprocessing consisted of resizing and normalization. Images in the dataset are resized into 224x224 and normalized by dividing the pixel value by 255 so the range of value is between 0 and 1.

A deep neural network needs a huge amount of data to achieve an adequate result. The fewer data available to train the network can make the learned network generalize poorly. To overcome this issue, data augmentation is implemented.

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Data augmentation can help with overfitting issues caused by the lack of data to use by increasing the size of the existing training dataset [10]. The augmentation techniques used in this study are rotation, shear, zoom, and horizontal flip.

2.4 Model Architecture

In this study, simple CNN was used as a baseline model, and two Deep CNN (ResNet50V2 and Xception) were used for transfer learning. For the simple CNN, it consists of three two-dimensional convolutional layers for feature extraction with kernel size of 3 and ReLU as activation function. In between the convolutional layer, there is a max-pooling layer for downsampling the images and at the end of the convolutional layer, there is a flatten layer to flattened the input from two-dimensional tensor to one-dimensional tensor. After the flatten layer, there is a fully connected layer with hidden neurons of 64 and a three-way output layer with softmax as the activation function. Before the output layer, there is a dropout layer that randomly sets the input unit to 0 to help prevent overfitting.

ResNet50V2 is a variant of ResNet50 model that has 48 convolutional layers with one max-pooling and average-pooling layer. The difference between the Resnet50 are last non-linearity layer has been removed and batch normalization and ReLU activation function are applied to the input before the multiplication with the convolutional operation [11].

ResNet50V2 has its convolutional layer is organized into a residual block that has a residual connection between each layer. The block becomes a shortcut for the identity function explicitly. The implementation of residual block could prevent the vanishing gradient problem. The residual block consists of a bottleneck layer that had kernel size of 1x1 which is continued with the 3x3 convolutional layer and ended by a 1x1 convolutional layer. The bottleneck layer is used because it can reduce the computational cost of the network by

minimizing the number of channels that are fed into the 3x3 convolutional layer [11].

Xception used modified depth-wise separable convolutional layer. It consisted of a 1x1 pointwise convolutional layer and was followed by a 3x3 depth-wise convolutional layer. Xception has 36 convolutional layers which have the purpose of feature extraction. The convolutional layers are organized as 14 modules and between each module, there is a linear residual connection [12].

2.5 Transfer Learning and Fine-Tuning

Transfer learning is a method that uses models that had been trained for a particular task and utilized its acquired knowledge to solved another task. In this study, transfer learning is done using pre-trained models that have been trained using ImageNet [13] dataset. The pre-trained models are Xception and ResNet50V2. Both models are then fine-tuned by unfreezing the top block or module of the frozen model base for feature extraction. After the feature extraction layers, classification layers are added. The classification layers consisted of one fully connected layer with 512 hidden neurons. L2 regularization is implemented to the layer kernel for preventing overfitting issues.

2.6 Training

The models were trained using Adam as an optimizer and categorical cross-entropy as loss function with a batch size of 10 for both training dan validation data. Callback was used to stop the model training when the validation accuracy is above a certain threshold. All of the models were trained using a learning rate of 0.001.

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2.7 Class Activation Maps

Class Activation Maps (CAM) are used to identify the sections of the image that gain attention by the model while making the final prediction, therefore it can provide insights into the working model. To obtain the class activation map, Grad-CAM is used.

Grad-CAM is a technique to visualize important sections for available classes using guided propagation. The technique uses the gradients of any targeted class and passes it through to the last convolutional layer in the network to highlight the important sections in the image for prediction [14]. Grad-CAM calculates the gradients with respect to the feature map generated from the convolutional layer. Class activation maps were generated for both benign and malignant tumors for all the models. Figure 2 shows the architecture of Grad-CAM, where y is the score of the class, and w is the weight of the last convolutional layer.

Figure 2 Block diagram of Grad-CAM on lung cancer detection

2.8 Evaluation Metrics

The performance of models was validated through evaluation metrics. In purpose to help models tuning, we used four metrics. Those are precision, recall, F1, and

accuracy. Precision tells about how accurate the model in terms of those which were predicted positive. Recall tells about the number of actual positives that the model was able to predict after labeling it as positive. F1 tells about how to balance precision and recall. AUC (area under curve) represents the degree of separability. Meanwhile, accuracy tells about how close the measured value to a known value. In mathematical definition, those metrics shown as below in Table 1.

Table 1 Evaluation metrics equation

Metrics	Equation	
Precision	$\frac{(TP)}{(TP + FP)}$	(1)
Recall	$\frac{(TP)}{(TP + FN)}$	(2)
F1	$2 \times \frac{(Precision \times Recall)}{(Precision + Recall)}$	(3)
Accuracy	$\frac{(TP + FN)}{(TP + TF + FP + FN)}$	(4)

3 Experimental Results and Discussion

In this section, various methods that have been used were evaluated to determine the efficiency of the proposed model. Keras API was used to load a pre-trained architectures model based on ImageNet Dataset before being tuned to our IQ-OTHNCCD lung cancer dataset. All computation work was done on a Google Compute Engine backend (GPU) with 13GB RAM, Nvidia Tesla P4 8GB GPU, Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU @ 2.30GHz CPU, and 69GB Disk.

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3.1 Result in terms of Testing Accuracy and Testing Loss

To get the most optimum training result of each model, parameters and hyperparameters were tuned while training. Training has been done using a maximum of 100 epochs for each model and stopped to the best weight using a callback. Also, balanced weight tests were given to several models to solve imbalanced data problems.

Table 2 Final testing accuracy and testing loss achieved by all architectures

Architecture	Testing Loss		Testing Accuracy	
	Non-Weighting	Weighting	Non-Weighting	Weighting
CNN	38.26	34.49	84.82	90.1
ResNet50V2	35.02	22.80	95.54	98.2
Xception	10.02	10.20	98.21	99.1

Table 2 shows that pre-trained models have a lower final loss and higher accuracy than the simple CNN model. Even more, when balanced weights were assigned to every model, the performance becomes increased. It could be said that the imbalanced data problem can be tackled by the weighting method [9]. The best-mixed loss and accuracy achieved by the Xception Weighting model.

3.2 Performance Analysis

Metrics value has been evaluated to test the further robustness of the model's performance. Those metrics are accuracy, precision, recall, F1, and AUC. Table 3 shows the higher accuracy, the higher the other scores. However, based on the theory, as the precision increased, the recall decreased, and vice versa [15]. To help optimize the result between precision and recall, F1 scores were calculated. Also, to simplify the selection of classification performance, the degree of

separability between the true positive rate and the false positive rate is represented by AUC (Area Under Curve) score. The best F1 score and highest AUC score are still achieved by the Xception Weighting model with a 99.11 F1 score and 99.99 AUC score.

Table 3 Result of evaluation metrics for the proposed models

Architecture	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC
CNN	84.82	90.00	80.36	84.91	96.32
ResNet50V2	95.54	95.50	94.64	95.07	99.79
Xception	98.21	98.21	98.21	98.21	99.94
CNN Weighting	90.18	90.09	89.29	89.69	96.98
ResNet50V2 Weighting	98.21	99.10	98.21	98.65	99.95
Xception Weighting	99.11	99.11	99.11	99.11	99.99

For validating the metrics score, confusion matrices for all architecture were obtained (Figure 3). The lack of benign data showed a low true positive value for benign classification. Again, weighted models showed an interesting performance. Compared to the Simple CNN model, CNN model with weighting method have improved benign true positive as much as 33%. Also, both ResNet50V2 Weighting and Xception Weighting showed almost perfect performance rather than without the weighting method.

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Figure 3 Confusion matrix for (a) CNN, (b) ResNet50V2, (c) Xception, (d) CNN Weighting, (e) ResNet50V2 Weighting, and (f) Xception Weighting.

The highest test accuracy (99.11) and AUC score (99.99) showed that the proposed model could be used as a supplement in clinical decision-making. Even though it is almost perfect, the final decision still has to be made by radiologists to validate the result.

3.3 Class Activation Maps Visualization Through Heatmaps

The class activation maps were plotted for each model. These class activation maps help localizing the section of the image that has a high probability of the existence of tumor and can be served as a guide for tuning the classifier. Figure

4 represents the activation maps in the form of heatmaps that had been superimposed with lung tumor image with the region that gain the network attention highlighted.

ResNet50V2 and Xception have a more defined focus on the targeted location than the simple CNN, although it still has offset from the ground truth tumor location. The lack of focus that exhibited by simple CNN model happened because it has shallower network than the other two models, therefore it could not extract low-level feature of the image as well as the other models [16].

The resulted Class Activation Maps from the two transfer learning models were accurate in detecting abnormal lung features generated from the tumor presence. Although it is not perfect, due to the low accuracy rate obtained by radiologist diagnostics [17], it is accurate enough for the visualization generated by the models to be used to help radiologists to pinpoint the location of lung tumors.

Figure 4 Visualization results of the class activation maps for CT scan malignant lung tumor corresponding to different architectures and weighting.

4 Conclusion

In 2020 there are 273 million lung cancer cases in Indonesia alone. To enhance the efficiency of lung cancer early detection, automatic analysis of cytological images to quantify the degree of abnormality from CT scan images and minimized false negatives are needed to shorten diagnosis time. Computer-aided detection using the DCNN method was conducted to classify CT scan images into benign and malignant cells. The comparative analysis between each model suggests a better performance for pre-trained models than simple CNN. Both pre-trained models, ResNet50V2 and Xception, have overcome our small dataset problem. Despite that, the weighting method also improved the proposed model performance to classify imbalanced data. The highest performance was achieved by the Xception Weighting model with 99.11% accuracy, 99.11% F1 score, and 99.99 AUC score.

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